

Project plan and monitoring framework (D1.1)

Project	HORIZON-ZEN - EU research programme beneficiary depositing solution in Zenodo
Work package	WP1 Project coordination and management
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Changes

Date	Version	Description
2023-06-21	1.0	Initial version
2025-09-17	1.1	Fixed broken link due to InvenioRDM documentation restructuring. Add note to internal links which are for project members only.

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Introduction

The overall project methodology is outlined in the project proposal (1.3 Project implementation methodology). This report provides extra details on the specific processes and methodologies that were outlined in the proposal.

Project management

The project uses a tailored version of the [PM2-Agile](#) process as described in the project proposal.

Life-cycle

The official project period (M1-M24) focuses mainly on the *planning* and *execution* phases, while most of the *initiating* and *closing* phases of the project are performed outside the official project period (e.g. initial proposal writing, and official closing and reporting).

Governance

The project is governed by the grant agreement between CERN and the European Union. The *project coordination board* provides advice to the project and is thus overall consulted and informed about the project, so that the project manager can take corrective actions based on the feedback.

Roles and responsibilities

Role	Members	Responsibility
Project coordination board	Blagovesta Cholova (EC) Dejan Dvorsek (EC) Jose Benito Gonzalez Lopez (CERN) Konstantinos Repanas (EC) Sonia Mentrída Calleja (CERN) Project manager (CERN) Team coordinator (CERN)	Coordinate project activities between CERN and the EC. Consulted on project activities in particular design proposals.
Project manager	Lars Holm Nielsen (CERN)	Responsible for the execution and success of the project including dissemination.
Team coordinator	Alex Ioannidis (CERN)	Responsible for coordination of the project team including sprint facilitation and planning activities.
Project team	Jenny Bonsak (CERN) Manuel Alejandro De Oliveira Da Costa (CERN)	Responsible for implementation activities.
Peer reviewer	Jose Benito Gonzalez Lopez (CERN) Nicola Tarocco (CERN)	Review deliverables prior to official release.

Work plan and schedule

The project has an overall work plan as laid out in the project proposal:

The project further refines the overall work plan and schedule through iterative planning:

- **Release planning:** The project has 5 official releases throughout the project, spaced roughly with 3 months intervals. The project manager is responsible for the release planning.
- **Iteration planning:** Each release is delivered through a series of development iterations (between 3-6 iterations). The project team is responsible for the iteration planning.
- **Iteration review/retrospective:** Each iteration ends with a review of work done towards the release, followed by a retrospective of the iteration.

Monitoring

The project manager tracks the current status of the work plan through a GitHub [project roadmap](#) (link only for project members).

Figure: Screenshot of the roadmap in Github.

Control

The work plan and schedule are being reviewed (to identify potential sources of delay; track changes, issues, and risks; as well as implement corrective actions):

- **Monthly:** By the project coordination board in their board meeting.
- **Weekly:** By the project manager and the project team coordinator in a reporting meeting.
- **Daily:** By the project team coordinator in daily standups.

Resources

Overall, the resource consumption is being tracked and reported through timesheets and the official financial reporting according to the project grant agreement.

The project manager monitors the overall consumption of person months per work package as detailed in the project proposal.

Issues and decisions

Project decisions are recorded in a [decision log](#) (link only for project members) by the project manager who also tracks the implementation of the decisions.

All issues related to the project are being logged in the project's [issues management](#) (link only for project members) on GitHub. The project manager is responsible for the overall issue management and review, supported by the team coordinator.

Risk management

Project risks are recorded and managed through the [project risk log](#) (link only for project members). The project manager is responsible for the overall risk management, supported by the team coordinator and the project coordination board.

Risks are identified and assessed through:

- The monthly, weekly, and daily work plan controls activity.
- Co-design activities (user testing, workshops, brainstorming).

The iterative development process and the co-design methodology are an intrinsic part of our risk mitigation strategy.

Requirements

Requirements are recorded in the [user stories registry](#) (link only for project members). Further requirements are collected through the co-design process and documented as part of the co-design methodology. The project manager is responsible for the requirements management, supported by the team coordinator and the project team.

Change management

Change management is overall governed by the grant agreement, meaning larger changes are subject to a grant agreement amendment. Management of further changes is handled and welcomed through the iterative development process.

Stakeholders management

Stakeholders are recorded in the [stakeholders registry](#) (link only for project members) on GitHub. The registry is maintained by the project manager. As the stakeholder registry will be publicly available, the registry will record roles instead of individual persons (e.g. REA project officer).

Quality management

Internal review

The project is subject to an internal review by CERN's IT Innovation Review Board through a review performed prior to the project's official reviews. Currently, we expect to conduct 2 internal reviews roughly at M12 and M24. Larger feature releases on Zendoo go through CERN's IT Change and Release Management Board.

Deliverables review

All report deliverables (including the data management plan) go through an internal peer review prior to the official submission.

Other official deliverables, which in HORIZON-ZEN is software, go through the defined processes for the [InvenioRDM development process](#).

Transition and deliverables acceptance

D4.1 Release and Deployment Strategy describes the processes around transition management and deliverables acceptance.

Key performance indicators (KPIs)

The project proposal defines clear KPIs to measure the success of the project throughout its duration as well as after the project ends.

Co-design

One of the project's specific objectives is to implement a community-driven methodology involving the EC, early adopters, and Zenodo/InvenioRDM partners, to foster speedy adoption/exploitation through targeted user requirements gathering, user testing, and validation of assumptions.

Design process

The InvenioRDM design process is based on Lean UX and works iteratively by gathering user stories from a few stakeholders, designing a prototype mockup, presenting and validating assumptions, reviewing against technical architecture, and gathering further requirements from a larger group of stakeholders. Overall, the goal is to elicit as many requirements and assumptions and ensure the technical feasibility of the implementation prior to writing the first code.

The process outputs user stories, mockups, and technical design documents documenting the user interactions and assumptions. The design documents are written collaboratively and iteratively.

Communication with stakeholders

Communication with co-design stakeholders is normally done on a one-on-one basis for the initial prototypes to ensure quality conversations, and through larger telecons with e.g. InvenioRDM partners in more questions & answers-style sessions.

Through the iterative process, demos are deployed to the Zenodo/InvenioRDM sandbox systems for testing and feedback, prior to finally being released on the production systems.

User feedback

Gathering and collecting user feedback is an integral part of the HORIZON-ZEN project. The goal is to validate and test assumptions as early as possible and thereby manage the risk of not meeting requirements of the EC and intended users.

User feedback is collected throughout all phases of the project:

- **Planning phase:** Based on technical design documents and mockup prototypes.
- **Execution phase:** Based on having the features deployed to demo, quality assurance and production systems through staged deployments.

The feedback is collected through:

- **Focus groups** - e.g. by presenting mockup prototypes at the project coordination board, for early adopters and in InvenioRDM telecons to facilitate in-depth discussions and gather collective feedback on various aspects of the solution.
- **Interviews** - in addition to focus groups, we will conduct meetings with key stakeholders and domain experts to gain deeper insights into their specific needs, expectations, and challenges.
- **User testing** - for specific features and overall usage we will conduct user testing sessions with selected stakeholders/early adopters which involve observing users as they interact with the solution - as user testing is resource intensive we will only be used for target features.
- **Suggestions** - we'll collect suggestions from Zenodo users, InvenioRDM partners and their users coming in our support lines, chat rooms and discussion forums. We may introduce a feedback option on Zenodo.org website as well.

Feedback Categorization

Feedback is documented and collected in the [user feedback logbook](#) (link only for project members) where it's categorized to help identify common themes, patterns, and areas requiring improvement. Feedback is further prioritized based on its impact and alignment with project objectives. The project manager is responsible for the integration feedback into the overall project development roadmap.